

A STUDY ON CRITICAL DIMENSIONS OF JOB SATISFACTION OF ACADEMICIANS AMONG COLLEGES IN COIMBATORE

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Cite This Article: R. Athi Sankar Lakshmanan, S. Selvakrishna, Dr. V. B. Mathipurani & Dr. D. Divya Prabha, "A Study on Critical Dimensions of Job Satisfaction of Academicians Among Colleges in Coimbatore", International Journal of Interdisciplinary Research in Arts and Humanities, Volume 4, Issue 1, Page Number 12-16, 2019.

Abstract:

Research shows that satisfied academicians are more efficient and productive so they positively influence organizational performance and work towards fulfillment of college objectives and goals. The main objective is to study about the level of satisfaction of Academicians using Kano's model and to know about the perception of Academicians towards their job using Kano's model. For this purpose a sample of 420 will be collected from the Academicians of textile industry were percentage analysis, factor analysis, regression and one way Anova will be used as tools to analyze the data. The conclusion is that several themes emerged from the overall result of the survey. The cause of concern here is that academicians have indicated that they need more for their compensation and from their superiors. Based on the results as a whole, without significant and meaningful improvement in Compensation, Faculty Co-operation, Training and Development, Performance Appraisal and Opportunity for career and promotion, the college current climate could eventually the Academicians's outlook and eventually their commitment to doing their job.

Key Words: Job Satisfaction, Academicians & Kano's Model

Introduction to the Study:

Academician's job satisfaction is the wording used to portray whether representatives are glad and satisfied and satisfying their wants and needs at work. Numerous measures implying that Academicians satisfaction is a factor in representative inspiration, representative objective accomplishment, and positive representative confidence in the working environment. According to Vroom "Worker Satisfaction is a positive introduction of a person towards a work part which he is by and by possessing". Academician's job satisfaction is a measure of how cheerful laborers are with their activity and workplace. Keeping assurance high among laborers can be of gigantic advantage to any organization, as cheerful specialists will probably create more, take less days off, and remain faithful to the organization. There are numerous elements in enhancing or keeping up high worker satisfaction, which insightful managers would do well to actualize. Academicians job satisfaction, while by and large a positive in association, can likewise be a misfortune if fair representatives stay since they are happy with your workplace. Numerous specialists trust that a standout amongst other approaches to keep up Academicians satisfaction is to influence laborers to feel like piece of a family or group. Holding office occasions, for example, gatherings or gathering excursions can enable form to close bonds among laborers. Numerous organizations likewise take part in group building withdraws that are intended to fortify the working relationship of the representatives in a non-business related setting. Outdoors trips, paintball wars and guided

hiking trips are adaptations of this sort of group building system, with which numerous businesses have discovered achievement. Obviously, couple of laborers won't encounter a lift in resolve in the wake of getting more cash. Raises and rewards can genuinely influence Academicians satisfaction, and ought to be given when conceivable. However cash can't comprehend all spirit issues, and if an organization with far reaching issues for laborers can't enhance their general condition, a reward might be immediately overlooked as the day by day worry of an unsavory activity keeps on mounting.

Satisfaction = f (what Academicians expects, their performance and excitement factors)

For the purpose of analyzing the critical dimensions Kano's model has been used towards analyzing the perception of employees.

Statement of Problem:

Academician's satisfaction is a state where individuals are not only happy with their current profiles but also look forward towards a long term association with the organization. No individual wants to quit his/her job after every six months. But the moment monotony creeps in, people start looking for better opportunities. Most of the times, Academicians s treat their jobs just as a mere source of earning their bread and butter. The need is that to know about the satisfaction of Academicians s through Kano's model so that the level of satisfaction can be increased in future period of time.

Objectives of the Study:

- To study about the level of satisfaction of Academicians using Kano's model.
- To analyze the demographic profile of the respondents.
- To know about the perception of Academicians s towards their job using Kano's model.
- To compare the demographic factors of the study with Academicians satisfaction.

Scope of the Study:

Kano model is used to determine the individual characteristics of the importance of Academicians satisfaction. Thus creating the necessary conditions of optimal, focused on product development and its evolution. The study will help the company to know about the perception of Academicians towards their job which leads to reduction in Academicians turnover of the company in future period of time. The study is based on factors such as Basic factor, Excitement factor and Performance factor.

Limitations of the Study:

- The study is been carried out only in colleges in Coimbatore.
- There is a chance of bias in collection of primary data from the respondents.
- The study is limited to 105 samples.
- Due to time constrains a deep analysis about the concept cannot be made.

Research Methodology:

Research Design: A research design is the specification of methods and procedure for acquiring the information needed. Research design classified under three broad categories – explanatory, casual and descriptive. But the researcher was concerned mainly with descriptive research design. The study was conducted in order to find out the Academicians satisfaction with colleges in Coimbatore.

Data Collection: Both the primary and secondary data are collected and used in the present study.

Primary Data: The primary data is collected from the respondents through questionnaire.

Secondary Data: The researcher collected the secondary data from books, journals, web sites etc. The data relating to the textile industry is collected from the manuals and the records of the respective colleges.

Sampling: Stratified random sampling method has been adopted for the selection of respondents in this study.

Sampling Design & Tools Applied:

Sampling Size: In this research, the sample size amounted to four hundred and twenty, which are surveyed from Academicians with colleges in Coimbatore.

Pilot Study: Before undertaking the complete data collection, a pilot study was conducted and then questionnaire was modified and restructured suitably.

Reliability Statistics	
Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
0.955	163

The above table shows about the reliability statistics of factors related to the questionnaire were 30 samples were taken for testing the reliability were the Cronbach's Alpha value is at 0.955 which shows that the items have relatively high internal consistency.

Tools Used for the Study: The statistical tool are applied viz. (a) Percentage analysis (b) One way Anova (c) Regression d) Factor analysis.

Analysis and Interpretation:

Demographic factors	Particulars	Frequency	Percent
Gender	Male	300	71.4
	Female	120	28.6

	Total	420	100
Age	21-25	12	2.9
	26-30	152	36.2
	31-35	128	30.5
	More than 35	128	30.5
	Total	420	100
Marital status	Married	28	6.7
	Unmarried	392	93.3
	Total	420	100
Years of experience	1-3 years	28	6.7
	4-6 years	220	52.4
	7-10 years	124	29.5
	More than 10 years	48	11.4
	Total	420	100

Interpretation:

71.4% are male and 28.6% are female. 2.9% are from the age group of 21-25, 36.2% are from the age group of 26-30, 30.5% are from the age group of 31-35 and 30.5% are from the age group of more than 35. 6.7% are married and 93.3% are unmarried in our survey. 6.7% are having 1-3 years of experience, 52.4% are having 4-6 years of experience, 29.5% are having 7-10 years of experience and 11.4% are having more than 10 years of experience.

Factor Analysis:

Factor Analysis For Basic Factors: A total of 16 variables were identified for the purpose of collecting expectations from the employees. In order to reduce the number of variables and to identify the key factors contributing towards the basic factors, factor analysis is performed. KMO and Bartlett's test is conducted to identify the sampling adequacy.

KMO and Bartlett's Test		
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy		0.513
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	1.13E+03
	df	120
	Sig.	0

KMO of sampling adequacy value for the basic factor measures is 0.513 and it indicates that the sample is adequate to consider the data as normally distributed. The number of factors as identified by performing the screen plot. The results are shown below,

Screen plot shown the above figure gives a pictorial view of the number of components to be shortlisted and to become factors based on Eigen value. So from the above chart become five factors have been shortlisted. Rotated component matrix is used to identify the factors after data reduction. The results are shown below,

Rotated Component Matrix^a					
	Component				
	1	2	3	4	5
Level of acceptance towards comfortable working hours	0.708	-0.158	0.481	0.126	0.029

Level of acceptance towards excessive workload well within the limit	0.707	0.121	0.05	0.437	-0.159
Level of acceptance towards adequate rest intervals	0.198	-0.181	0.727	0.414	-0.293
Level of acceptance towards adequate facilities provided to attend to their job	-0.159	0.238	0.334	0.718	0.002
Level of acceptance towards Working place free from dust, pollution, noise and proper lighting/ventilation	0.308	0.014	0.708	0.071	0.303
Level of acceptance towards colleagues treating them properly	0.099	0.798	0.117	0.253	0.149
a. Rotation converged in 12 iterations.					

Interpretation:

The common factors above 0.5 are taken for decision making process of the study. The factors are Level of acceptance towards comfortable working hours, Level of acceptance towards excessive workload well within the limit, Level of acceptance towards adequate rest intervals, Level of acceptance towards adequate facilities provided to attend to their job, Level of acceptance towards Working place free from dust, pollution, noise and proper lighting/ventilation and level of acceptance towards colleagues treating them properly.

One Way Anova:

Comparison Between Age of the Respondents and Acceptance towards Various Factors Related to Job Satisfaction:

		N	Mean	Std. Deviation	F	Sig
Level of acceptance towards working environment	21-25	12	3.6	0	83.339	0
	26-30	152	2.4632	0.71332		
	31-35	128	3.5312	0.71802		
	More than 35	128	2.5125	0.48391		
	Total	420	2.8362	0.8108		
Level of acceptance towards relationship with colleagues	21-25	12	3	0	48.946	0
	26-30	152	2.6579	0.52872		
	31-35	128	3.2812	0.35355		
	More than 35	128	2.4375	0.81085		
	Total	420	2.7905	0.67616		
Level of acceptance towards motivational and recognition	21-25	12	2.75	0	45.222	0
	26-30	152	2.6842	0.40967		
	31-35	128	3.3828	0.73705		
	More than 35	128	2.6172	0.63054		
	Total	420	2.8786	0.67703		
Level of acceptance towards salary	21-25	12	4	0	43.762	0
	26-30	152	2.9474	0.72596		
	31-35	128	3.625	0.72089		
	More than 35	128	2.7344	0.69853		
	Total	420	3.119	0.80726		

It depicts that there is no difference between age and level of acceptance towards working environment, relationship with colleagues, motivational and recognition and acceptance towards salary as the level of significance is at 0.000 which is lesser than 0.05 and the age group 21-25 (3.60) has higher impact towards all the factors and they disagree towards the factors.

Multiple Regressions:

Years of Experience and Acceptance towards Excitement Factors:

Coefficients						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.02	0.341		2.987	0.004
	Level of acceptance towards adequate canteen facilities	0.177	0.065	0.225	2.74	0.007
	Level of acceptance towards respondents happy with the company's policies	-0.121	0.069	-0.178	-1.754	0.082

Level of acceptance towards job security based on performance	0.423	0.064	0.657	6.62	0
Level of acceptance towards freely communicating their grievance	-0.03	0.082	-0.036	-0.36	0.719
a. Dependent Variable: Years of experience					

Years of experience (constant) 1.020= Level of acceptance towards respondents happy with the college policies (0.121)+ Level of acceptance towards job security based on performance (0.423)+ Level of acceptance towards freely communicating their grievance (-0.030). It shows that the factor level of acceptance towards job security based on performance is directly proportional to years of experience.

Findings:

- The factors level of acceptance towards comfortable working hours, Level of acceptance towards excessive workload well within the limit, Level of acceptance towards adequate rest intervals, Level of acceptance towards adequate facilities provided to attend to their job, Level of acceptance towards Working place free from dust, pollution, noise and proper lighting/ventilation and level of acceptance towards colleagues treating them properly are taken for decision making process of the study.
- Based on excitement factors the factors are level of acceptance towards adequate canteen facilities, level of acceptance towards respondents happy with the college policies, level of acceptance towards job security based on performance, and level of acceptance towards freely communicating their grievance are taken for decision making process of the study.

Suggestions:

- Provide Academicians well defined career paths (including succession plan), mentors and tuition remuneration for job-related education.
- Provide Academicians a clear professional development plan gives Academicians an incentive to stick around.
- Train supervisors in coaching and performance management skills.
- Implement a good promotion process, “soft skills” training development before and after promotion.

Conclusion:

The conclusion is that several themes emerged from the overall result of the survey. The cause of concern here is that academicians have indicated that they need more for their compensation and from their superiors. Based on the results as a whole, without significant and meaningful improvement in Compensation, Faculty Co-operation, Training and Development, Performance Appraisal and Opportunity for career and promotion, the college current climate could eventually the Academicians’s outlook and eventually their commitment to doing their job.

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